

a rusty brown appearance. Plants were stunted and affected foliage dried. Zn deficiency symptoms varied widely among varieties. Percentages of affected hills were averaged and varieties were grouped as tolerant (less than 3% affected hills), moderately tolerant (5-25% affected hills), susceptible (25-50% affected), and highly susceptible (50-100%). Only RAU4009-3 and RAU4005-26 were tolerant.

Shoot dry matter accumulation was markedly reduced by increasing Zn deficiency. Shoot weight, Zn concentration, P to Zn and Fe to Zn concentration ratio are in the table. Zn concentration was between 12.8 and 45.0 ppm, and was positively and significantly correlated with shoot yield ($r = 0.97^{**}$). There was a significant negative correlation with P:Zn (-0.95^{**}) and Fe:Zn (-0.97^{**}) concentration. Zn concentration was below the critical 19 ppm in highly susceptible varieties. Tolerant varieties had P:Zn > 192 and Fe:Zn > 7.6.

About 97% of the variability ($R^2 = 0.969^{**}$) in Zn responses was attributed to Zn concentration and P:Zn and Fe:Zn. The contribution of Zn and P:Zn are shown in the multiple regression equation

$$Y = 4.375 + 0.05^{**} X_1 + 0.014 X_2 + 6.286 X_3 \times 10^{-3^{**}}$$

Where,

Y = shoot yield,

X_1 = Zn content,

X_2 = Fe:Zn, and

X_3 = P:Zn.

(** denotes significance at 1 %)

Fe:Zn, however, did not contribute significantly to variability in Zn deficiency tolerance.

The study showed that Zn concentration and P:Zn could be a reliable tool for screening Zn-efficient varieties. $\mathcal{J}$

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Reaction of rice varieties grown in highly calcareous Fluvents to Zn deficiency, Bihar, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a	Shoot yield (t/15 plants)	Zn concentration (mg/kg)	P:Zn	Fe:Zn
RAU4009-3	T	0.6	41.6	132	6.0
RAU4005-26	T	0.6	45.0	129	5.7
IET6155	M	0.5	30.2	192	7.5
UPR82-1-7	M	0.5	33.5	176	7.3
RAU32-2-1	M	0.5	32.8	180	7.6
IR2071-586-5-6-3	M	0.5	35.0	171	6.7
IR36	S	0.4	20.6	286	13.8
IET4786	S	0.4	21.0	290	13.6
IET2881	S	0.4	22.6	265	12.8
Ratana	S	0.5	24.0	258	12.0
Prasad	S	0.4	23.5	255	11.1
Saket 4	S	0.4	20.5	317	12.2
Rajendra Dhan 201	H	0.3	15.5	406	16.5
Sita	H	0.3	13.5	459	19.1
IET3273	H	0.2	12.8	500	23.1
UPR304-40-2	H	0.3	16.5	388	18.2
UPR231-28-1-2	H	0.3	14.5	455	22.4
Pusa 33	H	0.3	18.5	351	16.4
Pusa 2-21	H	0.3	19.0	331	15.0

^aT = tolerant, M = moderately tolerant, S = susceptible, H = highly susceptible.

Varietal evaluation of rice in waterlogged saline soil

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Uniform variety trial-5 comprising 21 entries [including 2 local checks, Kalamota (sel), and SR26B], 8 genotypes found superior during the 1983 trial, and Pankaj (high yielding check) were evaluated at CSSRI,

Performance of 30 promising entries in waterlogged saline soil. Haryana, India. 1985.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Days to flowering	Spikelet sterility (%)	Plant survival at maturity (%)	Yield (g/plot)
CR117-215	105	75	137	38.7	7	15
CR292-5258	103	135	145	77.6	11	08
CR292-7050	109	100	140	39.4	12	40
CR221-1030	108	100	139	35.8	8	22
CN499-160-2-1	114	108	135	26.3	9	22
CN499-160-13-6	111	100	136	25.3	6	80
CN506-147-14-1	119	95	141	29.4	20	63
CN506-147-14-2	97	47	143	38.0	4	15
RPAR7360	—	—	—	—	0	—
NC498	118	117	172	17.3	24	147
OR456-30	122	67	140	51.1	14	15
TCA212	133	111	130	16.8	60	78
WC490	137	95	138	23.1	28	115
WC497	130	94	140	11.0	29	85
NC519	127	89	140	17.8	12	43
TCA72	139	108	128	22.4	44	160
PLA1100	—	—	—	—	0	—
NC513	124	78	140	31.3	44	153
NC492	137	142	137	18.1	56	348
Kalamota (sel)	139	105	136	13.4	68	392
SR26B	137	108	135	14.7	85	743
NC487/77	134	103	170	14.3	86	490
NC491	153	92	137	14.0	91	780
NC540	155	102	132	12.8	95	227
BKNPR-7601-4-1-2-3	150	89	145	62.0	81	250
BKNFR7601-4-1-9-2	146	91	136	40.6	88	345
SPR7295-53-1-2-1-2	123	81	144	31.0	90	212
Bowrah	125	61	135	23.6	40	157
IET6905	131	108	133	37.7	80	352
Pankaj	97	75	146	38.2	5	40
CD at 1%	—	54	—	33.2	25.4	297

Research Station Canning, West Bengal. The trial was in a randomized block design replicated 3 times in a 1-m-deep plot. All 30 entries were sown 22 Jun 1984 and transplanted on 23 Aug. Each entry was transplanted in 4 rows, at 30 hills/row. Spacing between rows and plants was 30 cm. Standing water depth at transplanting was 12 cm and surface soil (0-15 cm) salinity (EC_{sw}) in situ was 9.0 dS/m. Standing water depth during

crop growth was 29-58 cm in Aug, 47-50 cm in Sep, 41-51 cm in Oct, and 38 cm in Nov and Dec. The crop was harvested in Jan 1985.

Survival rate of the plants that survived to maturity ranged from 4 to 95% (see table). RPAR7360 and PLAI 100 did not survive. NC540 had maximum survival of 95%, followed by NC491 with 91%. Panicles/ m² ranged from 47 to 142, with NC492 producing

the most. CR292-5258 produced 135 panicles/m², but it also exhibited maximum spikelet sterility (77.6%). Kalamota (sel) had 68% survival and 105 panicles/m², whereas Pankaj had a survival rate of 68% and produced 75 panicles/m². The three highest yielding entries were NC491, 780 g/plot; SR26B, 743 g/plot; and NC487/77, 490 g/plot. Local check Kalamota (sel) yielded 392 g/plot. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

HYBRID RICE

Utilization of wide compatibility gene (S_5^n) for rice breeding

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F₁ hybrids of indica-japonica crosses show semisterility, while some wide compatibility varieties (WCVs) produce fertile F₁ plants when crossed with indica or with japonica varieties. We analyzed the genetic base for F₁ sterility and wide compatibility as follows. A set of multiple alleles was located between the *C* (chromogen for apiculus color) and *wx* (waxy endosperm) loci; S_5^n for WCVs, S_5^i for indica varieties, and S_5^j for japonica varieties, and the genotypes of S_5^n/S_5^i and S_5^n/S_5^j were fertile, but S_5^i/S_5^j was semisterile because of partial abortion of gametes carrying S_5^j . So far, some javanicas or derivatives such as Ketan Nangka, Calotoc, and CPSLO 17 have been found to possess S_5^n , and they also have the complementary genes for apiculus color, i.e. C^+ and A^+ . Since C^+ is closely linked with S_5^n , the progeny of indica/ WCVs or japonica/ WCVs showing apiculus color are likely to possess S_5^n .

We have selected several lines from Ketan Nangka (KN) crosses. The progeny of IR50//IR36/ Ketan Nangka showed indica-like plant type as well as good fertility of F₁ when crossed with japonica testers (see table). Likewise, some lines selected from

Characteristics of some promising lines with wide compatibility gene S_5^n , 1986.

Line	Cross or variety	Generation	Flowering date	Plant ht (cm)	F ₁ fertility	
					Tester	Fertility (%)
A1	Akihikari/NK4 ^a	F ₅	20 May	94	IR50	89.4
A9	Akihikari/NK4	F ₅	22 May	87	IR50	85.4
B5	Akihikari//Akihikari/NK4	F ₄	20 May	80	IR36	90.7
B20	Akihikari//Akihikari/NK4	F ₄	18 May	92	IR36	86.9
C1	IR50//IR36/Ketan Nangka	F ₅	29 May	92	Akihikari	83.5
C2	IR50//IR36/Ketan Nangka	F ₅	29 May	98	Akihikari	90.3
	Ketan Nangka		15 Jun	158	IR36	88.2
	Toyonishiki (check)		21 May	88	Akihikari	93.4
	IR36 (check)		4 Jun	81		89.1
	IR50/Akihikari F ₁ (check)		(test in 1983)			42.8

^a NK4 is an F₆ line from Nihonmasari/Ketan Nangka.

Akihikari//Akihikari/ (a line from Nihonmasari/ Ketan Nangka) showed normal F₁ fertility when crossed with IR36, although the lines are morphologically japonica type (see table).

The incorporation of S_5^n gene to indica or japonica breeding lines is expected to alleviate the sterility problem in indica-japonica crosses.

Specifically, those lines with S_5^n can be used for hybrid seed production, inasmuch as they would reveal high level of heterosis without F₁ sterility. As some IR varieties, including IR36 and IR50, possess a restorer gene for cytoplasmic male sterility of japonica type, indica-like lines with the S_5^n can be used directly as parents for hybrid seed production. *ℓ*

Pest Control and Management

DISEASES

Etiology of rice orange leaf

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In Thailand, Malaysia, and Indonesia, orange leaf is known to be associated

with mycoplasma-like organisms (MLO). Recent reports from China indicated that virus-like particles are associated with orange leaf.

We collected 34 rice plants with orange leaf-like symptoms from 6 Philippine sites. *Recilia dorsalis* nymphs